

Fix for Snakemake Job Submissions waiting unnecessarily on SLURM Clusters

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Fix for Snakemake Job Submissions waiting unnecessarily on SLURM Clusters

1.1 Author

Filipe G. Vieira – The GLOBE Insititute, University of Copenhagen

1.2 Description

This work item fixes an issue where Snakemake would not submit more jobs, even though there were available resources.

1.2.1 Problem

Snakemake 8.17 introduced a regression in the SLURM executor related to the `--max-jobs-per-second` option. When using a SLURM profile with `job: unlimited`, `cores: all`, and `--max-jobs-per-second: 1`, Snakemake would only submit one job at a time, even when sufficient resources were available. This behavior differed from Snakemake 8.16, where multiple jobs were submitted concurrently under the same configuration. The issue stemmed from the fact that `--max-jobs-per-second` had no default value, causing Snakemake to effectively limit submissions to one per second, even when more resources were available.

1.2.2 Solution

This work addresses the regression by ensuring that the `--max-jobs-per-second` option is handled correctly by the SLURM executor. The fix ensures that when `--max-jobs-per-second` is not explicitly specified, Snakemake submits jobs concurrently, taking advantage of available resources. This restores the behavior of Snakemake 8.16 and allows users to control the submission rate as intended.

1.3 Impact

This fix allows for a more efficient usage of computational resources by Snakemake, as well as potentially speeding up workflows runtime.

1.4 Associated Project Workitem

- [Issue 3019 - Snakemake only submits one job at a time...](#)
- [PR 3399 - fix: Re-evaluation of free resources](#)

1.5 Acknowledgement

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